

EFFECT OF SNAKE VENOM ON THE CYTOCHROME-CYTOCHROME OXIDASE SYSTEM

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The effect of (i) fresh solutions of cobra venom, (ii) solution of venom heated at different temperatures and (iii) of solution containing an active fraction of the venom, on the oxidation of *p*-phenylenediamine by the cytochrome-cytochrome oxidase system has been investigated. The results show that the venom contains an active principle which can strongly inhibit the cytochrome-cytochrome oxidase system.

It has been reported by us in a previous paper (this *issue*, p. 359) that the oxidation of substrates like glucose, lactic, pyruvic and succinic acids is strongly inhibited by cobra venom even at a low concentration. The inhibition has been attributed to the action of the venom on the cytochrome-cytochrome oxidase system. This view, however, can be easily subjected to experimental test. The effect of cobra venom on the oxidation of *p*-phenylenediamine by the cytochrome-cytochrome oxidase system has therefore been investigated. It has been reported previously (Ghosh *et al.*, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1936, **13**, 450, 627 ; 1937, **14**, 604) that this venom contains the proteolytic enzyme, trypsin which may destroy the cytochrome oxidase. For this reason, experiments have been carried out using solutions (p_H 7.4) of venom heated previously to a temperature at which the trypsin is destroyed. It has been found that even when trypsin is destroyed by heating, the solution of venom strongly inhibits the oxidation of *p*-phenylenediamine. Attempt has also been made to separate the inhibitor from cobra venom. The results of all these experiments are recorded in this paper.

EXPERIMENTAL

Effect of Fresh Solutions of Venom on the Oxidation of p-Phenylenediamine in Suspensions of Pigeon brain cells

Substrate used.—*p*-Phenylenediamine hydrochloride has been employed as the substrate in the present investigation. A 0.5% solution of the hydrochloride in phosphate-Ringer-Locke solution, neutralised to p_H 7.0 before use, was used. The final concentration of the substrate in the reaction mixture was 0.167%.

Source of Enzyme.—Pigeon's brain tissue was used as the source of the enzymes. Immediately after decapitation of the animal, the brain was taken out, kept in the frigidaire for a few minutes, and then minced into a fine paste.

Measurement of Oxygen Absorption.—The oxygen absorption was measured in the Warburg manometers at $37.5^\circ \pm 0.1$ and the experimental procedure was the same as described in the previous paper (*loc. cit.*).

Weighed quantities (about 50 mg.) of brain were put into each of a series of Warburg flask, and broken up in phosphate-Ringer-Locke solution of p_H 7.3. Adequate amount of the venom in phosphate-Ringer was also added. Suitable controls were kept side by side.

The substrate solution (1 c.c.) was kept in the side-tube of some of the Warburg flasks, while the same volume of Ringer was put into the side-tubes of the other flasks which served as control. The inner cup of each flask contained 0.2 c.c. of 20% KOH solution and a roll of filter paper. The total volume of liquid in each flask was 3.0 c.c. The flasks were attached to the manometers and shaken in a thermostat at 37.5 ± 0.1 for 1 hour and 30 minutes to allow sufficient time to the venom to exert its full effect on the enzymes in question. Next, the liquid in the side-tube was tipped off into the main compartment, the taps were closed and the oxygen absorption was measured during 1 hour at intervals of 15 minutes. The results are shown in Table I.

TABLE I

The effect of cobra venom on the cytochrome-cytochrome oxidase system

Conc. of substrate = 0.167% in each case.

No. of expt.	Venom (mg./c.c. of suspension).	Cu. mm. of oxygen absorbed per g./hr. by				Substrate.	% Inhibition.	
		Brain	Brain + substrate.	Brain + venom.	Brain + venom + substrate.		Obs.	Mean.
1	0.033	260	3200	60	180	5	97	
2	"	300	2900	80	220	4	95	96
3	0.0167	220	2540	80	220	4	94	
4	"	200	2600	100	300	3	93	94
5	0.0033	220	3520	140	2002	3	43	
6	"	200	3420	120	1780	4	49	46
7	"	240	3600	160	2040	4	45	

TABLE II

Brain taken = 50 mg. Conc. of the substrate 0.167% ; air

No.	System.	Manometer readings in mm.						
		Time (min.) after addition of the substrate						
		5.	10.	15.	25.	30.	35.	40.
1.	Brain after shaking for 1 hour with substrate	12	22	35	55	65	74	81
2.	Brain after shaking for 1 hour with 0.1 mg. of venom + substrate	1	3	7	8	9	10	11
3.	Brain shaken for 1 hour with 0.1 mg. of venom and then 0.1 c.c. of cytochrome-c + substrate added	1	3	7	9	11	12	13
4.	Brain shaken for 1 hour and then 0.1 c.c. of cytochrome-c + substrate added	13	26	41	62	73	83	91

From the results in Table I, it is evident that cobra venom in minute doses can inhibit strongly the cytochrome-cytochrome oxidase system. Thus the inhibition with 0.0033 mg. of venom per c.c. of brain suspension is about 50%, while with 0.033 mg. per c.c. the inhibition is as much as 96%.

To determine whether this inhibitor affects cytochrome-c or cytochrome oxidase, a solution of cytochrome-c was prepared by the method of Keilin and Hartree from ox heart (*Proc. Roy. Soc.*, 1937, **B**, 122, 298) and the effect of cytochrome-c on the inhibition of oxidation of *p*-phenylenediamine by cobra venom was noted. The results are shown in Table II.

The results in Table II indicate that cytochrome-c does not restore the oxygen uptake to the normal value after the venom has acted upon the brain cells. Therefore, the venom has either no action on cytochrome-c, or it affects simultaneously both cytochrome oxidase and cytochrome-c.

As stated already, the observed effects of cobra venom on tissue respiration may be attributed to the proteolytic digestion of the cytochrome oxidase by the trypsin present in the venom. In order to test this point, the effect of heating on the proteolytic and the inhibitory activity of cobra venom has been investigated.

Effect of Heating on the Proteolytic and the Inhibitory Activity of Cobra venom

A 5% solution of cobra venom in phosphate buffer (p_H 7.4) was heated at the desired temperature for 30 minutes and then cooled. The tryptic activity of this solution was estimated by allowing 1 c.c. of it to act on a mixture of 8 c.c. of 1% casein and 6 c.c. of phosphate buffer of p_H 7.4. The mixture was incubated for 2 hours at 37.5° in a thermostat, and at the end of this period, 5 c.c. of the solution were withdrawn and the acid liberated was titrated by 0.02N-KOH solution by Sørensen's method. The results are recorded in Table III. The inhibiting effect of this solution on the cytochrome-cytochrome oxidase system was measured in the Warburg's apparatus in exactly the same way as was done in the case of the venom solution used without heating. The results are recorded in Table IV.

TABLE III

Effect of heating on the tryptic activity of cobra venom

Venom heated for 30 mins. at.	0.02 N-KOH required after digestion (I).	Control (II).	Diff. bet. (I) & (II)
30°	2.90 c.c.	2.20 c.c.	0.70 c.c.
65°	2.22	2.20	0.02
70°	2.20	2.20	0.00

From the results recorded in Tables III and IV, it appears that although the tryptic activity of the solution of cobra venom is completely destroyed at about 70°, yet its power of inhibiting the cytochrome-cytochrome oxidase system remains unaffected up to about 80°. It is thus evident that the inhibition of the cytochrome-cytochrome oxidase system by cobra venom is not due to the trypsin contained in it.

TABLE IV

Effect of heating on the inhibiting power of cobra venom.

Conc. of venom in the medium = 0.0033 mg./c.c.

Cu. mm. of oxygen absorbed per g./hr. by

No. of expt.	Temp. at which the venom soln. heated for 30 min.	Brain.	Substrate.	Brain + substrate.	Brain + venom.	Brain + venom + substrate.	% Inhibition.
1	30°	316	3	3640	160	1680	54
2	70°	280	4	3040	132	1514	50
3	75°	252	4	3260	130	1620	51
4	80°	272	3	3510	145	1862	47

TABLE V

The tryptic activity of the purified material

0.02 N-KOH required

Material tested.	Conc. of the material in mg./c.c. of the soln.	after digestion (I).	Control (II).	Diff. between (I) & (II).
Cobra venom	3.0	3.4 c.c.	2.5 c.c.	0.9 c.c.
Purified material	3.0	2.5	2.5	0.0

TABLE VI

The inhibiting power of the purified material

Cu. mm. of oxygen absorbed per g./hr. by

No. of expt.	Purified material (mg./c.c. of suspension).	Brain.	Substrate.	Brain + substrate.	Brain + venom.	Brain + venom + substrate.	% Inhibition.
1	0.033	242	3	3420	70	388	90
2	0.033	310	4	3670	85	358	92
3	0.033	280	3	3284	82	535	85

Separation of the Inhibitor from Cobra Venom.—The presence of a separate active principle in cobra venom responsible for the inhibition of the cytochrome-cytochrome oxidase system having been established, attempts were made to isolate the inhibitor in a purified state from the crude venom. The inhibitor was separated from the trypsin in the following way.

An 1% solution (100 c.c.) of cobra venom in water was adjusted to p_H 9.0 and treated with 20 g. of pure sodium chloride in small amounts at a time. The solution was kept at 37° for about 30 minutes and then filtered. The filtrate was found to contain the inhibitor. The precipitate was dissolved in 50 c.c. of water, the p_H adjusted to 9.0 and 10 g. of pure sodium chloride were added slowly. The solution was kept at 37° for 30

minutes and filtered. The precipitate was rejected. The filtrates were combined and dilute H_2SO_4 was added to lower the p_H to 2.0. The precipitate formed was separated by filtration and dried in a vacuum desiccator over fused $CaCl_2$. The tryptic activity and the inhibiting power of the dry precipitate have been estimated. Its nitrogen content has also been determined by the micro-Kjeldahl method. The results are recorded in Tables V and VI.

The results recorded in Tables V and VI show clearly that the partially purified material is devoid of any tryptic activity, but possesses quite strong inhibiting action on the cytochrome-cytochrome oxidase system.

C O N C L U S I O N

Cobra venom, in minute doses, can inhibit the cytochrome-cytochrome oxidase system markedly. This is one of the main causes of the inhibition of tissue respiration by cobra venom.

The inhibition of cytochrome-cytochrome oxidase system by the venom is not due to the trypsin present in it.

The inhibitor has been partially purified.

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